

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORCE MAJEURE IN VARIOUS JURISDICTIONS AND ITS CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

The Force Majeure doctrine is one of the important legal instruments in modern private law, which ensures the fair distribution of liability rights of the contracting parties, when the performance of the obligations becomes impossible due to events beyond the parties' control. Its legal concept varies substantially in different jurisdictions: in English law it is fully regulated by contract law, the French model perceives it as a statutory category, German law links force majeure to the doctrine of hardship and American law defines it by adding impossibility, impracticability and frustration of purpose. These differences allow for different legal assessments and raise many questions about a universal and common definition.

The importance of force majeure in recent times has particularly emerged during the pandemic. Moreover, the significance of its scope has also been particularly evident in parallel with technological developments. The indicated factors have significantly changed the list of cases that can be considered as Force Majeure in specific cases which raised the question about how efficiently the classical doctrine responds to modern risks.

The aim of the article is to present the legal meaning of Force Majeure, its substantive elements and aspects, differences between jurisdictions and analysis of contemporary challenges. The article presents the reasons for the modernization of Force Majeure provisions, how and why the boundaries of its application are changing in modern context and why it is necessary to systematize the approaches existing in different jurisdictions. It is important to emphasize that the practical significance of force majeure shall only be fully functional if legal systems adequately adapt to technological, economic and climate changes.

Keywords: Force majeure; Unforeseeable events; International jurisdictions; COVID-19; Cybersecurity risks

Introduction

The Force Majeure doctrine has significant value in a private law, as it provides a fair distribution of liability rights of the contracting parties when the current developments are beyond the control of the parties. From a historical perspective, Force Majeure was mainly associated with natural disasters and military actions of states, although today its scope has significantly expanded, considering the circumstances and instances occurring in parallel with global development.

Post-pandemic, limited significance of the Force Majeure and practical challenges were particularly evident. In that period, courts of different countries made different legal assessments, demonstrating that the Force Majeure doctrine is a complex legal system and its interpretation depends on jurisdiction, formulation of contract terms and specific socio-economic reality. Considering the circumstances, modern contracts are closely integrated with digital reality. In connection with cybersecurity challenges, issues are increasingly being highlighted, and a few problems are emerging that do not generally fit into the classic force majeure categories.

The relevance of the research is conditioned by the fact that the legal systems of different countries have different approaches to the definition and application of the Force Majeure. English, French, German and American models differ both in terms of doctrinal grounds and practical application, which is why there is often ambiguity, legal disbalance and high risk of disputes between parties in international agreements.

Therefore, a comparative study of Force Majeure is important both from a theoretical and a practical point of view. The article reviews the legal nature of Force Majeure, its significant aspects, modern developments and an analysis of approaches of different jurisdictions. Accordingly, both issues regulated at the legislative level, as well as their practical aspects, are combined and reviewed.

The aim of the article is to understand the current relevance of force majeure, its functional purpose and contemporary challenges, to identify the main challenges that prevent the efficient use of the Force Majeure doctrine in legal practice. The article presents a legal vision designed to the requirements of modernity, aimed at improving the stability of international agreements and legal relations between the parties, which ensures the legal certainty for the parties and the observance of standards of fairness precisely in situations that are beyond the parties' control.

Literature Review

The legal essence of force majeure

Definition of Force Majeure

Force Majeure (Latin for "vis major") is sometimes translated into English as "Act of God," but literally translated as "superior force." It refers to unexpected events that make it impossible for the parties to a contract to fulfill their obligations. It includes subsequent impossibility cases, i.e. external events that occur after the conclusion of the contract and are beyond the control of the party for reasons such as: Fire, flood, drought, earthquake, civil unrest, terrorist attacks and

etc. causes and circumstances that make the performance of a party's contractual obligations not only excessively burdensome, but also impossible, whether temporarily or permanently (Berger, Behn, 2020).

The Roman concept of force majeure is the basis for the formation of a general idea in modern European legal systems. Force Majeure, in its essence, refers to a circumstance that is insurmountable for the parties and independent of their control, when it is impossible to fulfill the terms of the contract. The presence of the Force Majeure must impede the performance of the certain obligation and failure to perform the obligation should be present. In the event of Force Majeure, the non-performance of an obligation is justified for a period that is reasonable considering the impact of the obstacle on the performance of the contract (UNIDROIT, 2016, Art. 7.1.7).

Force Majeure and Hardship - both mechanisms exempt the parties to the contract from fulfilling their obligations, however, at the same time they regulate fundamentally different cases and accordingly create different legal outcome. Force Majeure applies when an unforeseen and irresistible event makes performance objectively impossible. The obstacle has to be beyond the control of the party, even if unavoidable with due diligence. Force majeure exempts the party from liability for non-performance for as long as the Force Majeure lasts and, in some cases, may justify termination of the contract. In contrast to the above, Hardship defines circumstances where performance is possible, but the balance/terms of the contract have fundamentally changed due to unforeseen changes in circumstances. In this case, performance is not impossible. On the contrary, sometimes it is excessively burdensome and economically unreasonable for one party. Unlike Force Majeure Hardship does not justify non-performance. Instead, it gives a precondition for renegotiation of the contract terms and if the latter is not fulfilled, termination of the contract is also possible. (Konarski, 2003).

Functionally, Force Majeure is a mechanism for excluding liability, while Hardship is contract adjustment mechanism. Therefore, the mechanisms in question represent two different instruments for the preservation of fairness and stability in contractual relations in the event of unforeseen circumstances (Brunner, 2009).

Classic elements of Force Majeure

Force Majeure is based on three key elements: irresistibility, unpredictability and externality.

The cause of irresistibility is usually caused by natural or physical events (e.g. earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, etc.), man-made events (for instance terrorist attacks) or a combination of both. The refers to events or situations which are unavoidable and/or insurmountable. In *Rainbow Warrior (France v. New Zealand Arbitration, 1990)* case it was explicitly defined that the inference of Force Majeure is justified only when the conduct of the party, performing the obligation is effected by an event which is entirely beyond its control, unforeseeable and so powerful as to make the performance of the obligation physically impossible despite all reasonable efforts. By the same definition,

the element of insurmountably implies not simply a difficulty or obstacle, but a circumstance that makes it impossible to fulfill an obligation despite all possible efforts (Hentrei, Soley, 2025).

Despite the exercise of reasonable efforts, unpredictability in the modern standard of Force Majeure is considered not as the absolute impossibility of prediction, but as a high probability of an objectively inaccurate prediction. Therefore, a party cannot invoke Force Majeure when the circumstance is considered part of the risks encountered in its field of activity. For example, parties involved in commercial relations are obliged to take into account normal seasonal fluctuations, typical risks of transportation or other standard events that may be associated with the above. Therefore, foreseeable or probable obstacles automatically exclude force majeure.

UNIDROIT Principles, CISG (United Nations, 1980) and international arbitration practice expressly acknowledges that Unpredictability is related not to the theoretical rarity of an event, but to whether it could reasonably have been included in the assessment of risks at the time the parties signed the contract. Subsequently, if certain political tensions, financial crises or epidemiological situation were already evident at the time the contract was concluded, their further deterioration often does not meet the criteria of unpredictability.

As for the third element of Force Majeure - Externality, it determines whether the circumstance causing the non-fulfillment of the obligation involves the action, desire or contribution of the party. Simply put, Force Majeure only applies when an obstacle is created by external forces and is not caused by the party itself. For instance, when the actions of a State create obstacles to the performance of specific obligations, it cannot invoke Force Majeure and use it to avoid liability (*Libyan Arab Foreign Investment Company v. Republic of Burundi, 1991*).

Force Majeure and Freedom of Contract

In modern times, human desires are boundless and one of the most efficient ways to realize them is by concluding a contract, where the terms and statements of the parties are formulated (Kotz, 2012). The contractual relationship foresees risk sharing too, however, even when the parties have complete autonomy in assuming and planning obligations, their contract shall not foresee all possible scenarios or/and outcomes, especially when circumstances arise in real life that are completely beyond human control. Therefore, under these circumstances the Force Majeure doctrine appears as a natural limit to contractual freedom, since the parties are no longer able to act with contractual freedom, because the party is deprived of the opportunity to fulfill its obligation due to reasons beyond its control.

In fact, the Force Majeure mechanism brings contractual relations closer to reality and protects the party from unfounded liability. The parties are also given the opportunity to define the framework of Force Majeure in the contract themselves as its action cannot be used in a way that violates the principle of good faith.

Force Majeure in International Standards

UNIDROIT Principles (2016) - develops one of the major provisions regarding Force Majeure: A party is free from liability only if the existing impediment was truly "unavoidable", the stated requirement affirms the principle of "reasonable steps to overcome the impediment".

Furthermore, the existence of Force Majeure does not automatically mean that the party is completely free from liability, since in such a case the party is obliged to take all reasonable measures and implement appropriate responses to overcome the existing obstacle or mitigate the consequences caused by it. According to international practice, "reasonable steps" include tracing alternative ways to fulfill the terms of the contract, if it is not unreasonably burdensome to fulfill, It is also eligible to use the assistance of a third party, as well as offer and implement partial performance, temporary changes to operational processes may be considered and of course, the most important - the notice requirement. The latter should be done in a timely manner, as late provision of information is likely to cause more problems. In fact, established practice reinforces the good-faith standard of force majeure., which entails the party's active conduct and the analysis of the specific impediment (UNIDROIT, 2016, Art. 7.1.7).

United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods (CISG) developed by the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law and adopted in 1980 is one of the most important legal documents for the interpretation of international commercial contracts. The CISG is currently valid in more than 90 countries and provides predictable and uniform legal standards for international trade. The concept of Force Majeure in the Convention is regulated by Article 79, which is considered one of the most important provisions in international law regarding liability exclusion mechanisms. The criteria for Force Majeure in this case foresee that the existing situation should not be subject to the control of the party. The CISG also requires a high standard of foreseeability. The party is obliged to prove that it was impossible to foresee the risk apart from those at the time of conclusion of the contract. The party shall justify as well that there were no reasonable alternatives, tools or resources through which performance would have been possible. In agreement with the CISG, the existing obstacle has to be objectively and practically insurmountable. A duty to inform is also expressly defined and its delay binds the party to compensate for damages. The specified standard is much stricter, since it does not acknowledge hardship. If the performance by a party is complicated but still possible, Force Majeure cannot be applied. In this case, only objective impossibility is considered. According to the definition set out in CISG 79, even when circumstances are complicated, if performance was technically doable, force majeure is not permissible. CISG (79) is often referred to as the "international force majeure benchmark" (Horobets, 2014).

ICC Force Majeure and Hardship Clauses

International Chamber of Commerce's 2020 Force Majeure Clause has become an international standard following the pandemic COVID-19 when a necessity

arose for a modern and flexible definition of practical Force Majeure in international trade. Accordingly, the approach outlined is distinguished by a highly practical approach, focused on the rapid changes in the global business environment. The 2020 model includes classic Force Majeure elements and for the first time considers circumstances such as epidemics, cybersecurity breaches, international sanctions, economic restrictions between countries etc. This focuses on unexpected sanctions announced by the state, which may prohibit the export/import of products, which may constitute Force Majeure but obviously, this does not consider and imply foreseeable political risks. It should be noted that in the latter case, the obligation to provide information is more strictly defined, namely, it provides for the provision of information immediately after the relevant event occurs, and delay may become the basis for independent liability.

Force Majeure in Different Jurisdictions

Legal regulation of Force Majeure in Georgia

The regulation of Force Majeure in Georgia is based on the general rules established in the Civil Code. The legal structure of National Law relies on the principle of good faith, the necessity of fulfilling contractual obligations and standards of party liability, which largely coincide with international practice (UNIDROIT, CISG), although it is distinguished by certain peculiarities.

In general, force majeure is not separately regulated in Georgian contractual law. In contrast, Georgian contractual law, which is based on German law, uses the category of "impossibility of performance". Therefore, a simultaneous release from both the obligation of performance and the obligation to compensate for damages is not systematic. Articles 394 and 404 of the Civil Code are not regulated by the indicated approach. In addition, the issue of secondary rights such as withdrawal (405) or price reduction (492) and others is unclear. In addition, there is no established concept of Force Majeure in Georgian law, with its prerequisites - inevitability, unexpectedness, and external nature. Moreover, there is no established concept of Force Majeure in Georgian law with its prerequisites - inevitability, unexpectedness, and external nature. In Georgia, the acknowledgement of Force Majeure the legal role and significance of the debtor's warranty liability remain unclear, as the warranty represents a tightening of the scope of liability, however, if Force Majeure exempts from liability, then it becomes meaningless whether the scope of liability for the debtor will be tightened or not (Sirdadze, 2019).

Force Majeure in German and French National Law and at the EU level

France is the birthplace of the doctrine of the Force Majeure. Following the 2016 reform, Force Majeure was defined in the French Civil Code by Article 1218, which requires the presence of three elements: Exteriorité — external nature, Imprévisibilité – The unforeseen event, i.e. the event at the time of the conclusion of the contract, must be "unpredictable" and Irrésistibilité. According to the said article, if the obstacle is permanent, the contract concluded between the parties is automatically terminated and the parties are released

from their obligations in accordance with the conditions provided for in Articles 1351 and 1351-1. During the proceedings, the judge has to establish that the event referred to by the debtor was so intense that he could not have resisted it. The judgment of the First Civil Chamber of the Court of Cassation of 6 November 2002 (Clio "Voyages Cultures" v. T., Juris-Data No. 016221) establishes that the inevitability and unpredictability of its performance, the occurrence of which has to be assessed at the date of conclusion of the contract, constitutes Force Majeure. The occurrence of Force Majeure is a foundation for exemption from liability, which is a general principle of French law applicable in the field of liability, whether contractual, tortious or quasi-delicta.

As for Germany, cases of Force Majeure are not directly regulated by the German legal code. In accordance with German law, such events may be subject to the statutory provisions on impossibility of performance, as set out in Section 275 of the German Civil Code and to the provisions concerning circumstances where existing events prevent the performance/basis of the transaction (Section 313 of the German Civil Code). According to Article 275, the obligations stipulated by the contract are not fulfilled if it is impossible for the debtor or another person to fulfill such obligations. A party may also refuse to fulfil its obligations under the contract if this requires unreasonable costs and efforts. Article 313 provides for a case where circumstances have changed significantly, in which case the terms of the contract may be modified (if possible) or terminated. In both cases, the parties are obliged to return any component of performance (if any) or payment received or to provide compensation if the performance cannot be "returned" (Rößler, 2007). There is no universal definition of force majeure in EU law. Despite this, the EU has taken significant steps in recent decades to create a general legal system. EU case law is largely based on documents and soft law sources such as PECL (Principles of European Contract Law), UNIDROIT Principles of International Commercial Contracts and DCFR (Draft Common Frame of Reference). Although they have no binding force, their influence is firmly established in modern European law. PECL - uses the term "excuse due to impediment", which enrolled not only classic Force Majeure, but also hardship, thereby reducing the imbalance between national laws. In this case, the same three criteria exempt a party from liability.

The wording is largely based on the common understandings of German and French law, although it is more flexible than them. The PECL referred to is considered a "common European agreed language" and is widely used by EU institutions at the stages of preliminary consultation documents.

The DCFR (Draft Common Frame of Reference) is a developed and more precise version of the PECL, the approach of which is even more systematic, its legal framework practically reflects the modern vision of the European Union on contractual liability, that the assessment of Force Majeure be economically realistic and verifiable (Study Group on a European Civil Code & Research Group on EC Private Law, 2009).

Common law – England

Under English law, Force Majeure does not represent a general legal doctrine, it is not regulated at the legislative level and does not have a corresponding legal definition. The application of the Force Majeure principle and its legal consequences arise only if the parties have specifically included a Force Majeure clause in the contract. Accordingly, the legal consequences are determined considering the terms agreed upon at the time of conclusion of the contract and the principles of its interpretation.

In the event of Force Majeure, a party is exempted from liability that falls within the categories expressly stated or implied in the contract is beyond the reasonable control of the party, could not have been reasonably foreseen at the time of conclusion of the contract and could not have been avoided even when exercising reasonable efforts.

If the contract does not contain a Force Majeure clause, non-performance is governed by the doctrine of frustration, which applies only when the occurrence of an event radically alters the obligations stipulated in the contract. Thus, Force Majeure in English law functions as a special, pre-agreed risk-sharing mechanism that requires clear and precise formulation (Symons & Dalby, 2022).

United States of America

The USA does not have a unified legal approach to Force Majeure, while each Federal State has complete legal independence. A National Law project was drafted to establish a unified legal policy- Uniform Commercial Code (UCC), which applies to the sale of goods, commercial transactions and business-related relationships. After several revisions over the years, the UCC has been adopted almost unchanged in almost every state in the United States.

Only Louisiana has not implemented a major part of the UCC, the reason for which is that Louisiana law is not based on Anglo-American Case Law, but on the French Civil Code. In the American case, if the contract provides a specific list of Force Majeure, such as "fire, epidemics, governmental orders" etc.

The court relies on this list, but if the contract is vague, the definition is narrowly implemented, which differs from the continental European approach, where courts can sometimes interpret according to the circumstances and/or consider the principle of hardship. In the USA, state intervention is minimal and the allocation of risks is entirely the responsibility of the parties. In fact, in the USA, Force Majeure is not just a legal concept, but also a mechanism of economic and social responsibility.

Modern challenges in Force Majeure

Force Majeure has become one of the most dynamic issues in modern law, parallel with globalization, technological progress and international economic relations. Although historically force majeure was associated with natural disasters, war and state actions, the challenges arising nowadays significantly go beyond the traditional understanding.

The COVID-19 pandemic has sharply highlighted the problems associated with the institution of force majeure. Although most treaties included Force

Majeure provisions, majority of them often did not foresee global epidemics. These problems were revealed in several areas, including judicial practice, in particular, countries assessed the degree of foreseeability of the pandemic in different ways. Court decisions on the same case differed, in parallel, international business began to update/interpret standard Force Majeure clauses so that future possible pandemics could be considered as Force Majeure that the parties to the contract do not face the same problem (Berger, Behn, 2020).

Most modern contracts depend on technological developments on databases, electronic payments and communication platforms. Therefore, a cyberattack can become an “obstacle” to the performance of a contract. In addition, this disruption can lead to the paralysis of business worldwide. The problematic issue is that neither national nor international standards adequately define whether a cyberattack can be considered a circumstance beyond the control of a party to the contract. According to Judicial practice, companies are obligated to have sufficient cybersecurity measures in place and based on this, cyberattack is not always considered unforeseeable event.

Likewise, the above-mentioned ICC and UNCITRAL have presented several problems, namely, different force majeure standards apply in international treaties, since the assessment of the same cases varies depending on the geographical location and multilateral treaties further complicate the invocation of force majeure.

In this regard, it is worth noting that in the modern economic environment, Force Majeure clauses are often used unfairly. This includes cases where companies are trying to avoid economic loss, which is their own commercial risk and in the context of COVID-19, some have even used minor delays to avoid liability.

In such cases, the necessity of a causal connection and the existence of three criteria (unforeseeable, uncontrollable, unavoidable) and the real definition of an objective obstacle to performance became even more evident (Kiraz & Yıldız Üstün, 2020).

Research Methodology

The article uses several research methods, which allow for a systematic review of the topic and understanding of the main specifics, without which it would be impossible to fully present the article. First, it is worth noting the descriptive method, which involves the presentation of existing legal norms and practices, the definition of specific issues and concepts without their critical evaluation and comparison. The purpose of this is to explain the legal structure of the concept of force majeure and, in fact, play a decisive role in the presentation of the legal systems of various jurisdictions.

Furthermore, its relevance lies in its ability to make the presented research more accessible and understandable, since the analysis of each issue is much easier through the information base established on the information obtained.

The descriptive method is chronologically followed by the systematic research method, which includes the classification of legal norms and approaches,

through which an in-depth analysis is later carried out. This method was used to establish a logical structure of the information received on Force Majeure. In addition, within the framework of the used literature, a legal analysis of national and international legislation and approaches, articles and books were carried out.

The comparative legal method should be emphasized too, through which the approaches to regulating Force Majeure were analyzed in the jurisdictions of various countries, including continental and common law systems.

The aim of this was to identify the common principles of Force Majeure and the existing differences from different legal systems. Through these research methods, the main specifications and approaches of this topic were greatly simplified and identified, which in each specific case more effectively and logically connects the information sources related to the research topic.

Results

According to the results of the study, the doctrine of Force Majeure is an important mechanism of contractual law, the purpose of which is to exclude the liability of the parties to the contract in specific cases when the fulfillment of the obligation becomes impossible due to reasons beyond the control of the party.

Through an analysis of different legal systems, it has been established that although Force Majeure has one common purpose, its interpretation and application can vary significantly depending on country, while in some countries the legislator precisely defines the concept of Force Majeure, in some countries the legal system does not provide a precise definition and it mainly depends on the terms of the contract concluded between the parties and the legal practice of a particular country.

It is also important to note that modern global processes and emerging problems, such as pandemics, conflicts between states and others, significantly increase the practical assignment and importance of this topic. Accordingly, a unanimous and clear definition of the Force Majeure doctrine nowadays will make it much easier to properly protect the rights and balance the interests of the parties involved in a legal relationship.

Conclusion and recommendations

Force Majeure, by its very nature, is one of the most important institutions of private law, the main purpose of which is to fairly distribute responsibility between the parties, when the performance of a contract is objectively impossible. The legal nature of Force Majeure, its elements and the standard of application vary significantly across countries and jurisdictions, accompanying circumstances and the rapid pace of multilateral development intensifies these differences.

The legal systems presented in the article also differ in English law the existence of Force Majeure mainly relies on the will of the parties, as it is not a doctrine established by law and its effect is determined by the terms agreed upon in the contract. In contrast to the mentioned, under French law it is a legally recognized legal institution, where the main elements are foreseeability, irresistibility and externality. The German model is more flexible and considers the principle of hardship,

In the USA, it is regulated by an agreement between the parties. These differences demonstrate that Force Majeure is not a universal concept for all countries and depends on legal, economic and cultural aspects. In turn, modern global processes give the meaning of Force Majeure a completely new content.

First, a clearer and more precise definition of the concept of Force Majeure is desirable to include in both international and national legislation, which would reduce the number of legal disputes in contractual relations.

When drafting contracts, it is also important for the parties to define more precisely the list of Force Majeure circumstances and their legal consequences, which will help to better protect the interests of the parties to the contract.

Obviously, the development of judicial practice will play a major role in shaping consistent case law regarding the assessment of Force Majeure, especially in cases involving global problems.

Therefore, according to the research presented, the doctrine of Force Majeure requires not only a new interpretation and acquisition of meaning, but also a systematic update. Therefore, it is important to systematize international standards, consider new types of risks, clearly distinguish between hardship and Force Majeure and legally distribute the burden of proof between the parties to the contract.

This is exactly the consistent and international systematic approach that ensures the preservation of the fundamental purpose of Force Majeure, which ensures a fair balance between the interests of the parties.

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